

A Summary of the CMIP5 Experiment Design

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1. Preface and overview.

At a September 2008 meeting involving 20 climate modeling groups from around the world (i.e., most of the major groups performing climate change research today), the WCRP's Working Group on Coupled Modelling (WGCM), with input from IGBP's AIMES, agreed on a new set of coordinated climate model experiments, to be known as phase five of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP5). The purpose of these experiments is to address outstanding scientific questions that arose as part of the IPCC AR4 assessment process, improve understanding of climate, and to provide estimates of future climate change that will be useful to those considering its possible consequences. As in past CMIP phases⁵, results from this new set of simulations is expected to lead to climate information and knowledge of particular relevance to future international assessments of climate science (e.g., the IPCC's AR5, now scheduled to be published in 2013). Consequently, for the compelling science motivations and for the interest in the IPCC AR5, the CMIP5 simulations will become a high priority on the research agendas of most major climate modeling centers. *CMIP5 is meant to provide a framework for coordinated climate change experiments for about the next five years and thus includes simulations for assessment in the AR5 as well as others that extend beyond the AR5. CMIP5 is not, however, meant to be comprehensive; it cannot possibly include all the different model intercomparison activities that might be of value, and it is expected that various groups and interested parties will develop additional experiments that might on and augment the experiments described here.* In the IPCC assessment context, it is expected that CMIP5 will provide information of value to all three IPCC Working Groups.

¹ There are many individuals who have contributed in substantive ways to this document. Pierre Friedlingstein, Olivier Boucher, Mark Webb, Jonathan Gregory, and Myles Allen have made particularly important suggestions and comments that have substantially altered and improved the design of the suite of long-term experiments. Additional helpful suggestions have been provided by: Sandrine Bony, Pascale Braconnot, Peter Cox, Veronika Eyring, Greg Flato, Nathan Gillett, Marco Giorgetta, Bala Govindasamy, Wilco Hazeleger, Gabi Hegerl, Chris Jones, Gareth Jones, Masihide Kimoto, Ben Kirtman, Corinne LeQuéré, David Lobell, Jason Lowe, Mike MacCracken, John Mitchell, James Murphy, Tim Palmer, Ben Santer, Cath Senior, Detlef Stammer, Bjorn Stevens, Tim Stockdale, Dáithí Stone, Peter Stott, and Keith Williams. Many others have contributed to the discussions that have led to the present experiment design. Apologies to those we have forgotten to include here.

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⁵ Phase 3 of CMIP (ca. 2004-2006) provided projections of climate change informing the IPCC's AR4. Additional simulations were collected more recently during phase 4 (Meehl et al., 2007), which provide information concerning the separate anthropogenic and natural influences on climate.

2. Introduction.

CMIP5 promotes a standard set of model simulations in order to:

- evaluate how realistic the models are in simulating the recent past,
- provide projections of future climate change on two time scales, near term (out to about 2035) and long term (out to 2100 and beyond), and
- understand some of the factors responsible for differences in model projections, including quantifying some key feedbacks such as those involving clouds and the carbon cycle

This set of aims has influenced the prioritization of the CMIP5 experiments.

A summary of the CMIP5 experiments is provided here, and the purposes of each simulation are enumerated. This integrated set of simulations addresses the priorities of several different communities and incorporates some of the ideas and suggestions from a number of workshops, meetings, and individuals, including the:

- Aspen Global Change Institute Workshop (July 2006)
- joint WGCM/AIMES meeting (Victoria, September 2006)
- Snowmass Energy Modeling Forum (July 2007)
- IPCC Expert Meeting on New Scenarios (Noordwijkerhout, September 2007)
- International Detection and Attribution Group (IDAG) meeting (Boulder, January 2008)
- WGCM meetings (Hamburg, September 2007; Paris, September 2008)
- WGNE meeting (Montreal, November 2008)
- the WGCM members and representatives from the individual modeling groups
- individuals who have commented on earlier versions of this document.

Some experiments included in CMIP5 were originally conceived as part of other model intercomparison projects (e.g., CFMIP and PMIP).

As noted above, under the CMIP5 strategy⁶ there are two distinct foci of the model experiments: 1) near-term simulations (10- to 30-years), some of which will be initialized with observed ocean state and sea-ice, and 2) long-term (century time-scale) simulations initialized from the end of freely evolving simulations of the historical period, which will be carried out with atmosphere-ocean global climate models (AOGCMs), which in some cases may be coupled to a carbon cycle model. CMIP5 also recognizes that some groups may wish to perform simulations with unusually high resolution atmospheric models or models with more complete treatments of atmospheric chemistry. When computer resources are insufficient to allow a fully coupled simulation, the option is provided to perform so-called “time-slice” experiments of both the present-day (AMIP period) and the future (specifically, the decade 2026-2035). In

⁶ Hibbard, K. A., G. A. Meehl, P. Cox, and P. Friedlingstein (2007): A strategy for climate change stabilization experiments. *EOS*, **88**, 217, 219, 221. Also, Meehl, G.A., and K.A. Hibbard, 2007: A strategy for climate change stabilization experiments with AOGCMs and ESMs. WCRP Informal Report No. 3/2007, ICPO Publication No. 112, IGBP Report No. 57, World Climate Research Programme: Geneva, 35 pp.

time-slice simulations of the future, projected changes in sea surface temperature (SST) and sea-ice obtained from a fully coupled atmosphere/ocean GCM's simulation will be imposed. Some modeling groups (e.g., in weather forecast centers) may also wish to perform some of the experiments in which sea surface temperatures are prescribed.

Individual groups may choose to perform either the near-term or the long-term experiments, or they may be able to do both. With certain models it may only be possible to perform the time-slice experiments.

We first provide a general overview of the CMIP5 experimental framework with schematic diagrams and two summary tables. Then in subsequent sections we provide a more detailed description of each experiment with the support of additional tables.

Due to the large numbers of simulations included in the CMIP5 framework, the experiments for both timescales are grouped into a "core" set, and then one or two "tiers" (Fig. 1). To allow for a systematic model intercomparison and to produce a credible multi-model dataset for analysis, the core experiments should be completed by all groups. The tier 1 experiments examine specific aspects of climate model forcing, response, and processes, and tier 2 experiments go deeper into those aspects. Thus one could think of the sequence, proceeding from core to tier 1 to tier 2, as a progression from basic to more detailed simulations to explore multiple aspects of climate system response and projections. There are fewer experiments in the decadal prediction set which accounts for the absence of a second tier. For each focus, it is recommended that groups address the core experiments first, followed by the tier 1 and tier 2 experiments, depending on interests and available resources.

Figure 1: Schematic of the two focus areas of CMIP5, with each one divided into prioritized tiers of experiments. The colors used in this figure are also used to indicate the relative priorities of the experiments summarized in the tables that appear later in this document.

To fill in the experiments outlined conceptually in Fig. 1, Figs. 2 and 3 show abbreviated summaries of the CMIP5 model experiments in schematic form. The decadal prediction experiments are shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Schematic summary of CMIP5 decadal prediction experiments.

Details will be given below regarding these experiments, but by way of introduction we note that there are two core experiments, one a set of 10 year hindcasts or predictions initialized from climate states in the years 1960, 1965, 1970, and every five years to 2005, with this last simulation representing the sole actual prediction beyond the present (i.e., beyond 2009). In these 10-year simulations, it will be possible to assess model skill in forecasting climate change on time-scales when the initial climate state may exert some influence. The other core experiment extends the 10-year simulations initialized in 1960, 1980, and 2005 by an additional 20 years. It is at this somewhat longer timescale that the external forcing from increasing GHGs should become more important. It is desired that at least three ensemble members be performed for each of the core experiments, with extension to at least 10 members as a tier 1 experiment.

The tier 1 near-term experiments also include predictions with 1) additional initial states in the 2000's when ocean data in particular is of better quality, 2) volcanic eruptions

removed from the hindcasts, 3) a hypothetical volcanic eruption imposed in one of the predictions of future climate, 4) different initialization methodologies, and 5) the option of performing high resolution time slice experiments with specified SSTs for certain decades in the future with a particular focus on 2026-2035. These time-slice experiments would also be appropriate for models that include computationally expensive atmospheric chemistry treatments. For models not used to do the long-term experiments, a relatively short “control” run and 1% per year CO₂ increase experiment are called for, and there is also the possibility of an atmospheric chemistry/pollutant experiment.

Turning to the CMIP5 long-term experiments, Fig. 3 shows the set of core experiments that include AMIP runs, a coupled control run and at least one 20th century experiment with all forcings (also referred to here as an “historical” run). There are two projection simulations forced with specified concentrations consistent with a high emissions scenario (RCP8.5) and a medium mitigation scenario (RCP4.5). For AOGCMs that have been coupled to a carbon cycle model (subsequently referred to as earth system models or ESMs), there are control, 20th century simulations, and a future simulation with the high scenario (RCP8.5) driven by emissions.

Figure 3: Schematic summary of CMIP5 long-term experiments. Green font indicates simulations that will be performed only by models with carbon cycle representation.

For the diagnostic core experiments (in the lower hemisphere), there are the calibration-type runs with 1% per year CO₂ increase to diagnose transient climate response (TCR), an abrupt 4XCO₂ increase experiment to diagnose equilibrium climate sensitivity and to estimate both the forcing and some of the important feedbacks, and there are fixed SST experiments to refine the estimates of forcing and help interpret differences in model response.

The tier 1 and tier 2 experiments explore various aspects of the core experiments in further detail. For earth system models, there are two carbon cycle feedback experiments. In the first, climate change is suppressed (by not letting the radiation code “see” the increasing CO₂ concentration), so the carbon cycle responds only to the changing CO₂. In the second, the climate responds to CO₂ increases, but the CO₂ increase is hidden from the carbon cycle. The surface fluxes of CO₂ will be saved in these experiments and compared with those from the corresponding “core” experiment in which the carbon cycle simultaneously responds to both climate and CO₂ concentration changes. From these fluxes, the strength of carbon-climate feedback can be expressed in terms of the difference in allowable emissions or in airborne fraction. There is a suite of cloud feedback experiments, some paleoclimate experiments to study the response of the models under much different forcing, experiments for climate change detection/attribution studies with only natural forcing or only GHG forcing (as well as some single forcing experiments), 21st century runs with the other two RCPs (RCP2.6 and RCP6), and extending the RCP future simulations out to year 2300. There are diagnostic experiments for additional feedback analyses with short 4XCO₂ experiments, an experiment to quantify the magnitude of the aerosol forcing, and a coordinated chemistry experiment called “AC&C4”.

Several of the experiments require specification of concentrations or emissions of various atmospheric constituents (e.g., greenhouse gases and aerosols). The Integrated Assessment Model Consortium will provide the Atmospheric Chemistry and Climate (AC&C) community the concentrations, emissions and time-evolving land use changes to be used in the simulations. Then AC&C will convert these data to global grids for direct use in the AOGCMs and ESMs according to the following tentative schedule: 1) pre-industrial values by the end of December, 2008, 2) historical values through 2005 by the end of March, 2009, and 3) for future scenarios (which are initiated in 2006) by the end of June, 2009. PCMDI will make these available to the modeling groups as soon as they have been received.

The near-term and long-term experiments are summarized in abbreviated form in Tables A and B below, with approximate estimates of the number of simulated years required in each case. Further itemized details of the experiments, including special output requirements for ESMs, will be provided in subsequent sections below.

It is of some interest to note that for CMIP3 (the climate model experiments that contributed to the IPCC’s Fourth Assessment Report), each modeling group submitted on average 1750 years of model output from the first member of what was often a multi-member ensemble of runs. Totaling the years across each model’s ensemble, we find on average nearly 2800 years per model, but the total varied substantially from one model to

another (500 to 8400 years with a median of 2200 years). Thus, the long-term and near-term CMIP5 “core” experiment suite, calling for at minimum ~2300 years, is comparable to that obtained from modeling groups in CMIP3, at least in terms of simulated years.

Table A: Summary of decadal prediction experiments and estimates of years of simulation. The first digit of each experiment number indicates in which subsequent table the experiment appears.

	#	Experiment	Core	Tier 1
Initialized with Observed Ocean State	1.1	Ensembles of 10-year hindcasts and predictions	3x10x10	
	1.2	Ensembles of 30-year hindcasts and predictions	3x3x20	
	1.1-E, 1.2-E	Increase ensemble sizes of 1.1 and 1.2		~7x10x10, ~7x3x20
	1.1-I	Initialize 10-year simulations from additional start dates annually in 2000s		≥3x(≥6)x10
	3.3	AMIP(1979- at least 2008)		≥30
	3.1-S	100-yr control		100
	6.1-S	1%/yr CO ₂ increase		80
	1.3	Hindcasts without volcanoes		≥3x5x(≥10)
	1.4	Predictions with 2010 Pinatubo-like eruption		≥3x(≥10)
	1.5	Initialize with alternative strategies		≥3x(≥10)
	1.6	Run with more complete atmos. chemistry		≥1x(≥10)
		SUBTOTALS:		480
“Time Slice”	3.3	AMIP (1979- at least 2008)		≥30
	2.1	Future “time-slice” experiment (2026-2035)		10
	3.3-E	AMIP ensemble		≥2x(≥30)
	2.1-E	Future “time-slice” experiment ensemble		≥2x10
	6.5-6.8	Cloud diagnostic experiments		≥105
		SUBTOTALS:		

Table B: Summary of long-term experiments and estimates of years of simulation. The first digit of each experiment number indicates in which subsequent table the experiment appears.

	#	Experiment	Core	Tier 1	Tier 2
ALL MODELS	3.1	Coupled model, pre-industrial control	≥500		
	3.2 & 3.2-E	historical (1850- <u>at least</u> 2005) ensemble	≥156	(≥2)x (≥)156	
	3.3 & 3.3-E	AMIP ensemble (1979- at least 2008)	≥30	≥2x(≥30)	
	3.4	Mid-Holocene (6 kyr ago)		≥100	
	3.5	Last Glacial Maximum (21 kyr ago)		≥100	
	3.6	Last Millennium (850-1850)			1000
	4.1, 4.2, 4.3, & 4.4	Projected responses to concentrations based on RCPs 4.5 & 8.5 (core) and RCPs 2.6 & 6 (tier 1)	2x95	2x95	
	4.1-L	Extension of RCP4.5 through year 2300		200	
	4.2-L & 4.3-L	Extension of RCP8.5 and RCP2.6 through year 2300			400
	6.1	Idealized 1%/yr simulations	140		
	6.2 a&b	Prescribed SST expts. to diagnose “fast” responses to 4x <u>pre-industrial</u> CO ₂	2x(≥30)		
	6.3	Diagnosis of climate system “slow” responses to abrupt quadrupling of CO ₂	150		
	6.3-E	Ensemble of 5-year simulations to diagnose “fast” responses to abrupt 4x <u>pre-industrial</u> CO ₂ increase.		11x5	
	6.4a & 6.4b	Prescribed SST expts. to diagnose “fast” responses to all anthropogenic aerosols and to sulfate aerosols alone (for the year 2000)		≥2x30	
	6.5, 6.6 & 6.8	Prescribed change in CO ₂ concentration (tier1), and “patterned” (tier1) and uniform (tier 2) changes in SST for diagnosing cloud responses.		2x≥30	≥30
	6.7a&b&c	Aqua-planet cloud responses (control, 4xCO ₂ and +4K experiments)		3x5	
	7.1 & 7.2	historical runs with only natural forcing and only GHG forcing		2x(≥)156	
	7.3	historical runs forced by individual agents			≥1x>156
	(7.1-7.3)-E	Additional ensemble members of 7.1-7.3			(≥1)x(≥2)x (≥)156
SUBTOTALS:			≥1226	≥1592	≥1898
ESMs	5.1	Pre-industrial control with CO ₂ concentration determined by model	≥251		
	5.2 & 5.3	Emission-driven historical and RCP8.5 simulations.	251		
	5.4 & 5.5	Diagnosis of carbon-climate feedback components in prescribed CO ₂ experiments (following “idealized” or more “realistic” pathways) in which CO ₂ surface fluxes are saved and allowable emissions computed.		140 or 251*	140 or 251*
	TOTALS:			≥1718	≥1727

In the following sections, the CMIP5 experiments are grouped into tables according to their primary objectives and the simulations are described in more detail:

- Table 1: “Decadal” prediction (hindcasts and projections), initialized with observed ocean state
- Table 2: Near-term “time-slice” experiments to accommodate computationally demanding models.
- Table 3: Baseline long-term simulations for model evaluation and for understanding historical and paleoclimates
- Table 4: Long-term climate projections.
- Table 5: For coupled carbon/climate models (earth system models or ESMs), additional simulations of the past and future.
- Table 6: Diagnostic experiments for understanding the long-term simulations.
- Table 7: Long-term simulations for detection and attribution of climate change.

3. Focus on the near term.

a. Decadal prediction (hindcasts and projections).

There is considerable interest in exploring the degree to which future climate states depend on the initial climate state, focusing in particular on whether we can more accurately predict the actual trajectory of future climate (including both forced and unforced change) if we initialize the models with at least the observed ocean state (and perhaps also sea ice and land surface). A broad set of coupled model experiments to explore the decadal prediction problem has been described in the document⁷ prepared by the WGCM/WGSIP/CLIVAR/ WCRP sub-group led by Tim Stockdale, and they are summarized in Table 1. An additional description of the new field of decadal prediction is given by Meehl et al. (2008)⁸.

Though some groups will target higher resolution versions of their models to better resolve regional climate and extremes in the decadal prediction experiments, high resolution is not a requirement, and the experiments would also be usefully performed with the same model used for the longer-term runs discussed in section 4 below.

⁷ “Coordinated experimentation to study multi-decadal prediction and near-term climate change”, WGCM/WGSIP/CLIVAR/WCRP sub-group (Tim Stockdale, Gabi Hegerl , Jerry Meehl, James Murphy, Ron Stouffer, Marco Giorgetta, Masihide Kimoto, Tim Palmer, Wilco Hazeleger, Detlef Stammer, Ben Kirtman and George Boer), 2008.

⁸ Meehl, G. A., L. Goddard, J. Murphy, R. J. Stouffer, G. Boer, G. Danabasoglu, K. Dixon, M. A. Giorgetta, A. Greene, E. Hawkins, G. Hegerl, D. Karoly, N. Keenlyside, M. Kimoto, B. Kirtman, A. Navarra, R. Pulwarty, D. Smith, D. Stammer, and T. Stockdale (2008): Decadal prediction: Can it be skillful? , *Bull. Amer. Meteorol. Soc.*, submitted.

Table 1. Summary of decadal prediction experiments.

	#	Experiment	Notes	# of years
CORE	1.1	Ensembles of 10-year hindcasts and predictions	With ocean initial conditions in some way representative of the observed anomalies or full fields for the start date, simulations should be initialized towards the end of 1960, 1965, 1970, 1975, 1980, 1985, 1990, 1995, 2000 and 2005. A minimum ensemble size of 3 should be produced for each start date. The atmospheric composition (and other conditions including volcanic aerosols) should be prescribed as in the historical run (expt. 3.2) and the RCP4.5 scenario (expt. 4.1) of the long-term suite of experiments.	3x10x10
	1.2	Ensembles of 30-year hindcasts and predictions	Extend to 30 years the expt. 1.1 integrations with initial dates near the end of 1960, 1980 and 2005. A minimum ensemble size of 3 should be produced for each start date.	3x3x20
TIER 1	1.1-E, 1.2-E	Increase ensemble size	Additional runs to expand each ensemble to a size of O(10).	~7x10x10, ~7x3x20
	1.1-I	Initialize 10-year simulations from additional start dates	As in 1.1 and 1.1-E, but initialized near the end of 2001, 2002, 2003, 2004, 2005, 2006 (2007, and beyond) to take advantage of the better ocean data of the Argo float era	≥3x(≥6)x10
	3.3	AMIP (1979-at least 2008)	This run is described in Table 3 (expt. 3.3).	≥30
	3.1-S	A shortened pre-industrial control	This is a shortened version of the pre-industrial control run described in Table 3 (expt. 3.1).	100
	6.1-S	1%/yr CO ₂ increase	An- 80 year run with a 1% per year increase in CO ₂ (a shortened version of expt. 6.1), initialized at year 20 of the control run (3.1-S).	80
	1.3	Hindcasts without volcanoes	Additional runs initialized near end of 1960, 1975, 1980, 1985 and 1990 as in expts. 1.1 and 1.2, but without volcanic eruptions (e.g., without Agung, El Chichon and Pinatubo).	≥3x5x(≥10)
	1.4	Predictions with 2010 Pinatubo-like eruption	An additional run initialized near end of 2005 as in expt. 1.1, but with a Pinatubo-like eruption imposed in 2010.	≥3x(≥10)
	1.5	Initialize with alternative strategies	Since there is at present no generally accepted “best” way to initialize models, some groups may choose to try different initialization methods.	≥3x(≥10)
1.6	Run with more complete atmos. chemistry	The chemistry/aerosol community plans to put together experiments with short-lived species and pollutants (probably two to three years hence).	≥1x(≥10)	

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b. “Time-slice” experiments with computationally demanding models.

The highest resolution and most comprehensive climate models require enormous computing resources, which will likely make it impossible to use them to complete the many multi-century simulations called for under the suite of CMIP5 experiments. An alternative is to perform “time-slice” experiments with atmosphere-only models forced by prescribed SSTs and sea ice (as in AMIP experiments). The surface boundary forcing (e.g., SSTs) must be obtained from future scenario runs performed with coupled atmosphere/ocean models that are less computationally demanding. “Time-slice” experiments offer opportunities to (for example) to:

- explore the implications of running climate models at high resolution,
- examine the regional effects of climate change at small scales where impacts are felt,
- study the air quality implications of climate change with models that include sophisticated treatments of atmospheric chemistry, and
- obtain more robust statistics characterizing changes in climate, in particular the likelihood of rare or extreme events.

The time-slice experiments are listed in the Table 2 below. *All years or ranges of years appearing here or elsewhere in this document should be interpreted as including all months from the beginning of the first year through the end of the last year (e.g., 1979-2008 is a simulation initiated on 1 January 1979 and ending on 31 December 2008).*

Table 2. “Time-slice” experiments for 1979-at least 2008 and 2026-2035.

	#	Experiment	Notes	# of years
TIER 1	3.3	AMIP (1979- at least 2008)	This run is described in Table 3 (expt. 3.3), but is also listed here with the understanding that models doing time-slice experiments with computationally demanding models would not likely be able to complete the core suite of long-term experiments.	≥30
	2.1	Future “time-slice” experiment (2026-2035)	Simulation of a future decade covering the years 2026-2035, with prescribed SSTs and sea ice concentration anomalies (relative to expt. 3.3) based on one of the following pairs of coupled atmosphere/ocean climate model runs: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> the difference in climatology between years 2026-2035 of RCP4.5 (expt. 4.1) and years 1979-2008 of the historical run (expt. 3.2), or the difference in climatology between years 2026-2035 of the RCP4.5 30-year run initialized from observations in the year 2005 (expt. 1.2) and a climatology for years 1979-2008 based on a subset of the years covered in the expt. 1.1 series of 10-year simulations (i.e., 1979-1980, 1981-1985, 1986-1990, 1991-1995, 1996-2000, 2001-2005, and 2006-2008 from the runs initialized near the end of 1975, 1980, ..., 2005, respectively) 	10
TIER 2	3.3-E	AMIP ensemble	Additional AMIP runs (expt. 3.3, but with different initial conditions imposed on the atmosphere and possibly also the land) yielding an ensemble of size ≥3 (and if practical, much larger).	≥2x30
	2.1-E	Future “time-slice” experiment ensemble	Additional expt. 2.1 runs (but with different initial conditions imposed on the atmosphere, sea-ice, and ocean and possibly also the land) yielding an ensemble of size ≥3 (and if practical, much larger). The changes in climatological SSTs and sea-ice used in prescribing the SST and sea-ice in these extended time-slice runs should, when available, be taken from more than one pair of coupled atmosphere/ocean model runs.	≥2x10
	6.5-6.8	Cloud diagnostic experiments	Prescribed SST experiments, consistent with CFMIP requirements, described fully in Table 6.	≥105

Further notes and issues that need to be considered include the following:

- 1) RCP4.5 is chosen as a “central” scenario, though choice of scenario does not make much difference for this timescale since the scenarios do not diverge much

before 2030. For consistency with the long-term prediction experiments (Table 4) RCP4.5 is chosen for the decadal prediction experiments.

- 2) Care must be taken in specifying changes in SSTs and sea ice for the period 2026-2035. Future *anomalies* obtained from the coupled model runs should be added to the observed present climate to get future SST and sea ice concentration. Special care must be taken to avoid sea ice concentrations dropping below 0% (or rising above 100%).
- 3) For the purposes of determining the PDFs of the altered future climate state relative to the present (and in particular to determine changes in the frequency of rare events), it would also be useful to perform these large ensembles of time-slice experiments with the atmospheric components of the coupled models used in the longer-term experiments (i.e., as opposed to higher resolution discussed here).
- 4) Rough estimates of model sensitivity and diagnosis of clouds and cloud feedbacks can be made by performing the additional prescribed SST experiments described in Table 6.
- 5) The nominal period for AMIP simulations is 1979-2008 (i.e., 30 years), but it is strongly recommended that these simulations be continued to the present (as SST and sea ice observations become available). This will allow comparison with some of the newest satellite data.

c. Decadal prediction experiment details

Core runs:

- 1.1 10 year integrations with initial dates towards the end of 1960, 1965, 1970, 1975, 1980, 1985, 1990, 1995 and 2000 and 2005 (see below), but extending through the end of the next 10 years.
Ensemble size of 3, optionally to be increased to O(10)
Ocean initial conditions should be in some way representative of the observed anomalies or full fields for the start date.
Land, sea-ice and atmosphere initial conditions left to the discretion of each group.
- 1.2 Extend integrations with initial dates near the end of 1960, 1980 and 2005 to 30 yrs.
Each start date to use a 3 member ensemble, optionally to be increased to O(10)
Ocean initial conditions represent the observed anomalies or full fields.

Further details on the core runs:

- Groups are expected to initialize their runs at some point prior to the 10-years (or 30-years) of the forecast period. As an example, the 10 year period beginning 1 January 1966 and ending 31 December 1975 could be initialized on some day late in 1965 (or on 1 January 1966). It is expected that most groups will initialize their models no earlier than 4 months prior to the calendar years of interest. Note that for simulations initialized towards the end of 1960, 1965, 1970, 1975, 1980, 1985, 1990, 1995, 2000, and 2005 the "years of interest" are respectively 1961-

1990, 1966-1975, 1971-1980, 1986-1995, 1991-2020, 1996-2005, 2001-2010, and 2006-2035.

- The actual length of the period simulated will include at least 10 (or 30) complete calendar years. Output should be reported from the point of initialization through the end of the last calendar year. As an example, a simulation initialized on November 1 1965 should end 31 December 1975, and output should be provided from all 122 months of this simulation.
- Choice of initial conditions is up to each group, subject to the principle that they should represent in some way the observed state of the climate system for the start date. Analyses of past ocean states and/or anomalies are available. Methods to transfer such analyses into an ocean model's initial condition exist. Most experience so far is of using observed anomalies on top of the coupled model climate, but initializing with the full state is also possible, and will be used by some groups, though the whole question of initializing the climate system presents one of the biggest scientific challenges of decadal prediction.
- All forcings should be included as observed values for past dates, with prescribed concentrations of well-mixed GHGs. The details should be the same as used in the CMIP5 historical (20th century) runs (see Table 3), with the same flexibility on the treatment of ozone and aerosol and the same specified observational datasets. Note that with the exception of experiment 1.3, aerosols from observed volcanic eruptions should be included in all of the simulations.
- For future dates, the RCP4.5 scenario should be used if possible. Specification of reactive species and aerosols will follow those used in the long-term projection runs (see Table 4). With the exception of experiment 1.4, assume that there are no volcanic eruptions in the future (i.e., after year 2009).
- Any deviations from the standard specifications should be properly documented.
- If sea-ice needs to be specified instead of being modeled, then “no cheating” applies: values cannot be specified using observations later than the start of the run. Persistence of ice from, for example, the year or decade prior to the start of the run is recommended.
- Note the treatment of volcanic aerosol: observed values should be used for past dates, as per CMIP5, but values to be used after 2005 should be specified based on the assumption of no further volcanic eruptions. The model runs are thus configured to predict what will happen to climate, relative to the observed past, if no major eruptions take place, which is a possible outcome for a thirty year period.

Tier 1 runs.

- 1.1-I 10 year integrations from near end of 2001, 2002, 2003, 2004, 2006, (2007...)
Each start date to use a 3 member ensemble, optionally to be increased to O(10)
Runs from 2007 onwards encouraged where possible
These runs make use of the recent well-observed upper 2000 meters of the ocean for temperature and salinity from the Argo floats, and are a step towards possible real-time prediction.

For those models that are able to produce 20th century climate runs, the CMIP5

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Deleted: Calendar start date can be 1st September, 1st November, 1st December or 1st January, according to the convenience of the modeling group.

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Deleted: Actual integration length should be long enough to produce 10 or 30 complete calendar years. It is likely that any extra 'initial' months would be discarded in the analysis.

20th century / RCP4.5 runs should be increased in number to create an ensemble of the desired size of continuous runs extending to 2035. Details as per CMIP5 long-term integrations. Ensemble size to match those used in 1.1 and 1.2.

These runs form a “control” against which the value of initializing near-term climate and decadal forecasts can be measured.

- 3.3 An AMIP run is called for to allow evaluation of the atmospheric model when subjected to observed SSTs and sea ice.
- 3.1-S, 6.1-S For models that do not have 20th century and other standard runs, a 100 year control integration is called for along with an 80 year run with a 1% per year increase in CO₂, starting 20 years into the control run. These integrations will allow an evaluation of model drift, transient climate response, and ocean heat uptake, and give some idea of the natural coupled modes of variability in the model.

(For groups that want to use an anomaly initialization method, a transient run with observed forcings might be run from the end of the control. With due consideration to the ‘cold-start’ problem, this could give a late 20th century model climate which could be compared to the observed ocean climate for the purpose of defining initial condition anomalies to be inserted into the model. However, this is considered part of the initialization method - it is up to each group to choose the most suitable approach, and data from such runs will not be collected.)

- 1.3 Additional runs from near the end of 1960, 1975, 1980, 1985 and 1990 without including volcanic eruptions (e.g., without Agung, El Chichon and Pinatubo) will enable an assessment of the impact of volcanic eruptions on decadal predictions. It also enables an estimate of “overall skill” of decadal prediction to be made, complementing a dual analysis of “expected skill conditional on no big volcano” and “possible impact of volcano”. These runs could either all be 10 years long, or the 1960 and 1980 runs could be 30 years to assess the longer term impact of the volcanoes.
- 1.4 Repeat of the 1.1 2005 forecast with an imposed “Pinatubo” eruption in 2010
- 1.5 Comparison of initialization strategies - for example, a repeat of runs (1.1) using an alternate initialization strategy or alternate initial data.
- 1.6 Impact of short lived species (chemistry) and air quality (experiment note yet formulated).

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4. Focus on the longer term.

a. Baseline simulations for model evaluation and for understanding historical and paleoclimates.

The long-term experiments that are most essential for model evaluation include a control run, an historical (1850-2005) run, and an AMIP simulation, which are all core experiments in Table B above. Additional experiments from the more distant past (PMIP experiments) provide further opportunities for model evaluation under very different conditions from present climate. The CMIP5 simulations summarized in Table 3 below can be performed both by coupled atmosphere/ocean models (AOGCMs) without carbon cycles and by coupled carbon/climate models (but with prescribed CO₂ concentrations). *As noted earlier, all years or ranges of years specified in this document should be interpreted as including all months from the beginning of the first year through the end of the last year (e.g., 1850-2005 is a simulation initiated on 1 January 1850 and ending on 31 December 2005).*

Table 3. Baseline simulations for model evaluation and for understanding historical and paleoclimates.

	#	Experiment	Notes	# of years
CORE	3.1	Pre-industrial Control	Impose non-evolving, pre-industrial conditions, which may include: Prescribed atmospheric concentrations of <ul style="list-style-type: none"> all well-mixed gases (including CO₂) some short-lived (reactive) species Prescribed non-evolving emissions or concentrations of <ul style="list-style-type: none"> natural aerosols or their precursors some short-lived (reactive) species. Unperturbed land use.	500 (after spin-up period)
	3.2	Historical (1850- <u>at least</u> 2005)	Impose changing conditions (consistent with observations), which may include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> atmospheric composition (including CO₂), due to both anthropogenic and volcanic influences solar forcing emissions or concentrations of short-lived species and natural and anthropogenic aerosols or their precursors. land use 	≥156
	3.3	AMIP (1979- at least 2008)	Impose SSTs & sea ice (from observations), but with other conditions (including CO ₂ concentrations and aerosols) as in expt. 3.2. See expt. 6.5 for further recommendations from CFMIP.	≥30
TIER 1	3.2-E	Historical Ensemble	Additional historical runs (expt. 3.2, but initialized at different points in the control) yielding an ensemble of size ≥3.	≥2 x ≥156
	3.3-E	AMIP Ensemble	Additional AMIP runs (expt. 3.3, but initialized with different atmospheric and possibly land-surface conditions) yielding an ensemble of size ≥3.	≥2x30
	3.4	Mid-Holocene (6 kyr ago)	Consistent with PMIP specifications, impose Mid-Holocene conditions, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> orbital parameters atmospheric concentrations of well-mixed greenhouse gases 	≥100 (after spin-up period)
	3.5	Last Glacial Maximum (21 kyr ago)	Consistent with PMIP requirements, impose Last Glacial Maximum conditions, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ice sheets atmospheric concentrations of well-mixed greenhouse gases 	≥100 (after spin-up period)
TIER 2	3.6	Last Millennium (850-1850)	Consistent with PMIP requirements, impose evolving conditions, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> solar variations volcanic aerosols 	1000 (after spin-up period)

Purposes and key diagnostics:

3.1 Pre-industrial control

- a) Serves as the baseline for analysis of historical and future scenario runs with prescribed concentrations.
- b) Estimate unforced variability of the model.
- c) Diagnose climate drift and for ESMs carbon cycle drifts in the unforced system.
- d) Provides initial conditions for some of the other experiments.
- e) Provides SSTs and sea-ice concentration for prescription (as a climatology) in expt. 6.2a.

3.2 Historical (mid-1800's – at least 2005)

- a) Evaluate model performance against present climate and observed climate change.
- b) Provides initial conditions for future scenario experiments
- c) Enables detection and attribution studies – evaluation of human impact on past climate (see expts. 7.1-7.3).
- d) For models with full representation of the carbon cycle, the surface fluxes of CO₂ will be saved in order to calculate allowable emissions implied by the prescribed changes in atmospheric CO₂ and the uptake/release of CO₂ by the oceans and terrestrial biosphere. The degree to which the model calculated emissions agree with observed emissions is a measure of model carbon cycle fidelity.
- e) The separate effects on the surface CO₂ fluxes due to climate change alone (i.e., the carbon-climate feedback) and due to CO₂ concentration changes alone can be estimated by comparing the allowable emissions or the airborne fraction in expt. 3.2 to those found in historical segments of expts. 5.4 and 5.5 (if option 2 is selected, as described in Table 5).

3.3 AMIP (1979- at least 2008)

- a) Evaluate model performance in uncoupled mode
- b) Determine whether errors seen in coupled model are also evident when sea surface temperatures and sea ice are prescribed
- c) For those groups carrying out the time-slice experiments (see Table 2) or CFMIP experiments (see Table 6), serves as the baseline for the SST perturbation experiments.

3.2-E Historical ensemble (mid-1800's- at least 2005)

- a) Better isolate the externally-forced response from total response (which is of particular importance in so-called detection and attribution studies), and obtain an estimate of the “unforced” variability as a residual.
- b) Enables assessment of statistical significance of differences between simulated and observed fields and between different simulations
- c) Better determine evolving climatology and the statistics of rare events.

3.3-E AMIP ensemble

- a) Enable assessment of statistical significance of differences between simulated and observed fields and between different simulations
- b) Better determine evolving climatology and the statistics of rare events.

3.4 Mid-Holocene (6 kyr ago)

- a) Compare with paleodata the model response to known orbital forcing changes and changes in greenhouse gas concentrations.
- 3.5 Last glacial maximum (18 kyr ago)
 - a) Compare with paleodata the model response to ice-age boundary conditions.
 - b) Attempt to provide empirical constraints on global climate sensitivity.
- 3.6 Last Millennium (850-1850)
 - a) Evaluate the ability of models to capture observed variability on multi-decadal and longer time-scales.
 - b) Determine what fraction of the variability is attributable to “external” forcing and what fraction reflects purely internal variability.
 - c) Provides a longer-term perspective for detection and attribution studies.

Further notes and issues that need to be considered include the following:

- 1) The length of the pre-industrial control run (after initial spin-up) should be long enough to extend to the end of each perturbation experiment that is spawned from it. In order to accommodate an historical run (~1850-2005) followed by a future scenario run (~2006-2300), we need a control run of at least 450 years.
- 2) The simulations in Table 3 are referred to as prescribed “concentration” runs since the well-mixed gases like CO₂ will be prescribed, not calculated from emissions. Other gases (e.g., ozone) might also be prescribed, but perhaps as a function of altitude, latitude, longitude, and month of year (i.e., seasonally varying). In some models reactive species might be calculated with simple chemistry models, while in others they might be prescribed. The same is true of aerosol species.
- 3) Specified land-use changes will be supplied to the modeling groups for 20th and 21st century climates, but the implementation of these datasets and whether or not to include dynamic vegetation is up to the individual modeling groups.
- 4) The land surface may change in these models due to imposed land use change, natural changes in vegetation characteristics (in response to climate change and increasing CO₂), and in some models due to succession of natural ecosystems (i.e. dynamic vegetation). For the AMIP experiment (3.3), CFMIP recommends that modeling groups turn off the terrestrial carbon cycle, which in some models may produce unrealistic vegetation; vegetation characteristics based on observations could be used instead.
- 5) Care must be taken in accounting for volcanic eruptions that occurred prior to 1850 and also in the future because this can especially impact sea level changes, which respond on multi-century time-scales. If we completely neglect volcanoes prior and after the historical period, then we shall exaggerate their effect on the historical sea level record because during this period the average forcing will become negative (relative to the pre-industrial control). If we include a background volcanic aerosol forcing in the pre-industrial control run, then the same background aerosol should probably be included in the future runs, otherwise there would be a slight exaggeration in the warming (and in sea level increases) throughout the future runs, which would almost certainly be unrealistic. However, imposing a background volcanic aerosol instantaneously in year 2006 of the “future” runs (see Table 1) would also be unrealistic because there were no

major volcanic eruptions in 2006. It is recommended that either volcanic aerosols should be omitted entirely from both the control and future runs, or, alternatively, the same background aerosol should be prescribed in both runs.

- 6) It is recommended that some representation of the solar cycle be included in the 20th and 21st century simulations, though that is left up to the discretion of the modeling groups.
- 7) For all simulations in this group (including the PMIP simulations) the atmospheric CO₂ concentrations will be prescribed, but there will be considerable interest in evaluating the carbon cycle component of ESMs. The carbon cycle module in these models should therefore be active (responding to the prescribed CO₂ concentrations) with all surface carbon fluxes saved. Any discrepancies between the simulated carbon budget and the observations will be of considerable interest.
- 8) The mid-Holocene and “last millennium” experiments (3.4 and 3.6) should be initialized from the pre-industrial control run, but the end of this run can extend beyond the end of the control.
- 9) In the last glacial maximum experiment (3.5) initialize all components except the ocean from the pre-industrial control; Initialize the ocean from a cold spun-up state provided by PMIP.
- 10) The ice sheet reconstruction to be used in the last glacial maximum experiment (3.5) will be provided by PMIP and will require changes to the surface elevation, land surface type and land fraction.
- 11) For groups choosing to specify (rather than calculate) the time-varying and evolving ozone concentrations, the most accurate option is to rely on a three dimensional (latitude, altitude, time) monthly mean ozone time series based on observations wherever available and based on model output for the period pre-1970 and in the future (consistent with the chosen RCP). Two options will be made available for use in CMIP5:
 - Option 1: A merged observationally-based and model-based dataset.
 - i. For the well-observed period (1979-2006): An activity under the auspices of SPARC will create a consensus observational stratospheric ozone database. The monthly mean database will be zonal means (5° zones) with global coverage, extending from the tropopause to 70 km at high vertical resolution (~1 km), and spanning the period 1979 to 2006 with no missing values. A fixed monthly mean tropospheric ozone climatology, on the same zonal and vertical grid, and representative of the period 1979 to 2006, will be appended to the transient stratospheric ozone fields to provide a seamless database. While this approach can be expected to provide the most accurate past stratospheric ozone forcing, fixed tropospheric concentrations are of course unrealistic and clearly cannot reproduce time-varying tropospheric ozone radiative forcing.
 - ii. For the “historical” period (1850-2006): Regression coefficients will be calculated for halocarbon effects (EESC) and/or linear trend and various known natural forcings (volcanic aerosol, solar, ENSO, QBO). The regression coefficients will be used to extrapolate that data back in time, and form a stratospheric ozone time series backward to cover the entire time period 1850-2006.

- iii. For the future (2007 and beyond): A similar procedure could be used to extrapolate into the future, and would capture changes due to halocarbons which will be an important driver of future ozone behavior. However, coupled chemistry climate model (CCM) simulations⁹ indicate that future stratospheric ozone abundance is likely to be significantly affected by climate change, and it is not yet possible to estimate this contribution statistically from observations. Therefore, the SPARC CCMVal activity is proposing to provide a stratospheric dataset for CMIP5 that extends the observational database into the future, based on CCM simulations that include the effects of climate change as well as halocarbon changes.
- Option 2: An entirely model-based dataset: A model-based vertically resolved, monthly mean, full atmosphere ozone and tropospheric aerosol database from 1850 to 2150 from CCM simulations for the entire time period, past and future, will be provided by AC&C activity 4. This has the advantage of being a physically consistent model dataset throughout time and space and including responses to all relevant forcings/composition changes such as methane and nitrous oxide trends since the pre-industrial. However, the models that have thus far expressed willingness to provide output to this activity are models that in general emphasize the troposphere, placing therefore less emphasis and computational resources on stratospheric physics and chemistry.

12) At the WGCM meeting in October 2011 there was agreement that it would be useful for model evaluation and detection/attribution studies to extend the CMIP5 historical runs (expt. 3.2) to near-present (as we have for AMIP), rather than ending them in 2005. In fact since the CMIP5 project is ongoing, it would be useful to have simulations extended to at least the end of 2012 using some estimate of recent and future forcing. There is, however, no community-wide accepted observationally-based concentration/emissions past 2005. Groups are therefore free to use whatever concentrations, solar forcing, SO2 emissions etc. they want to use in extending these runs. It is also o.k. for detection/attribution studies to simply splice one of the RCP runs to the end of the historical simulations.¹⁰ No matter what forcing is chosen it is important to consider the following:

- i. The groups should take care that there are no substantial discontinuities in the forcing in passing from the "past" to the "future", defined to be the end of 2005.
- ii. It is recommended that if an ensemble of "all-forcings" historical simulations have been run (expt. 3.2-E), then each member of the ensemble

⁹ Eyring, V., D. W. Waugh, G. E. Bodeker, E. Cordero, H. Akiyoshi, J. Austin, S. R. Beagley, B. Boville, P. Braesicke, C. Brühl, N. Butchart, M. P. Chipperfield, M. Dameris, R. Deckert, M. Deushi, S. M. Frith, R. R. Garcia, A. Gettelman, M. Giorgetta, D. E. Kinnison, E. Mancini, E. Manzini, D. R. Marsh, S. Matthes, T. Nagashima, P. A. Newman, J. E. Nielsen, S. Pawson, G. Pitari, D. A. Plummer, E. Rozanov, M. Schraner, J. F. Scinocca, K. Semeniuk, T. G. Shepherd, K. Shibata, B. Steil, R. Stolarski, W. Tian, and M. Yoshiki (2007): Multimodel projections of stratospheric ozone in the 21st century, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 112, D16303, doi:10.1029/2006JD008332.

¹⁰ If the user chooses to use an RCP forcing to extend an historical run, only historical ensemble members not used to initialize existing RCP runs need to be run past 2005, as the extended portion of other historical ensemble members would simply duplicate the beginning of the existing RCP run.

- should be carried to the end of 2012. Thus, a full ensemble of runs (through year 2012) would be available for analysis.
- iii. It is recommended that all historical runs with only a subset of forcing (see Table 7; e.g., GHG only, natural forcing only) should also be extended through the year 2012.
 - iv. If one of the RCP forcings is used to extend the historical run, it may not matter too much which RCP is chosen, and CMIP5 makes no strong recommendation. If a modeling group has no preference, they might choose the RCP8.5 expt., as at least one group (the Hadley Centre) has made this choice already.

b. Future climate projections.

A collaborative process involving the WGCM, AIMES, and the Integrated Assessment Modeling Consortium has produced four emission scenarios for future climate, one non-mitigated and three taking into account various levels of mitigation. These are called “representative concentration pathways” (RCPs)¹¹ that will begin in year 2006 and continue through the end of year 2300. The RCPs are labeled according to the approximate target radiative forcing at year ~2100 (e.g., RCP4.5 identifies a concentration pathway that approximately results in a radiative forcing of 4.5 W m⁻² at year 2100, relative to pre-industrial conditions). There is apparently some interest in considering separately the highly uncertain projected changes in land use, but these are not included in the CMIP5 experiments.

Table 4. Future climate projections with models forced by RCP concentrations.

	#	Experiment	Notes	# of years
CORE	4.1	RCP4.5 (2006-2100)	Radiative forcing stabilizes at ~4.5W m ⁻² after 2100. (if ESM, save CO ₂ fluxes from the surface to calculate allowable emissions)	95
	4.2	RCP8.5 (2006-2100)	Radiative forcing reaches ~8.5 W m ⁻² near ~2100. (if ESM, save CO ₂ fluxes from the surface to calculate allowable emissions)	95
TIER 1	4.3	RCP2.6 (2006-2100)	Radiative forcing peaks at ~2.6 Wm ⁻² near 2100.	95
	4.4	RCP6 (2006-2100)	Radiative forcing stabilizes at ~6 W m ⁻² after ~2100.	95
	4.1-L	RCP4.5 extended through year 2300	Extension of expt. 4.1 through the end of the 23 rd century.	200
TIER 2	4.2-L & 4.3-L	Extend RCP8.5 & RCP2.6 through year 2300	Extension of expts. 4.2 and 4.3 through the end of the 23 rd century.	2x200

¹¹ For a description of the RCPs, see Moss et al., 2008, report from the IPCC Expert Meeting Towards New Scenarios, held in Noordwijkerhout, The Netherlands, in September, 2007 (see <http://www.mnp.nl/ipcc/>, “IPCC New Scenarios”)

Purposes and key diagnostics:

4.1-4.4 Prescribed concentration scenarios (through year 2100).

- a) Provide estimates of future anthropogenic climate change across a range of future scenarios.
- b) Prescribed concentrations facilitate direct comparison between models with and without a carbon cycle component.
- c) In coupled carbon/climate models, allowable anthropogenic emissions of carbon dioxide can be inferred and the implications of carbon flux uncertainty can be estimated. The allowable emissions will also be used to explore the potential impact of various mitigation scenarios.
- d) The separate effects of the surface CO₂ fluxes due to climate change alone (i.e., the carbon-climate feedback) and due to CO₂ concentration changes alone can be estimated by comparing the allowable emissions in expt. 4.2 to those found in the 21st century segments of expts. 5.4 and 5.5 (if option 2 is selected, as described in Table 5).
- e) Tune EMICS and integrated assessment models to reproduce these results and then use the simpler models to consider many more scenarios.

4.1-L Extension of the RCP4.5 scenario to year 2300

- a) Provide an estimate of climate change and its implications (e.g., for sea level changes and carbon cycle changes), as projected further into the future.

4.2-L & 4.3-L Extension of the RCP8.5 and RCP2.6 scenarios to year 2300

- a) Explore the longer-term implications of a wider range of future scenarios.

Further notes and issues that need to be considered include the following:

- 1) There will be continuity of concentrations/emissions and in land use in transitioning from the historical to the future runs.
- 2) In these runs that project into the future, individual potential volcanic eruptions should be omitted, but a constant background volcanic aerosol may (or may not) be specified. In any case, care must be taken in treating volcanic aerosols, as discussed in the notes after Table 1.
- 3) See note 9) following Table 3 for options for specifying time-varying and evolving ozone concentrations.

c. Additional coupled carbon/climate model simulations of the past and future.

These simulations cannot be performed unless a model includes a global (land and ocean) carbon cycle component. Although the climatic importance of carbon cycle responses can be inferred from the prescribed concentration experiments described above, there is strong interest in exploring in a more direct way how carbon feedbacks have affected climate over the last century and how they might affect quasi-realistic scenarios of the future. Thus, fully coupled carbon/climate model experiments with prescribed anthropogenic CO₂ *emissions* (rather than the resulting concentrations) are of considerable interest.

With coupled carbon/climate models, there is also interest in determining what fraction of the total carbon cycle response is attributable to increasing atmospheric CO₂ concentration and what fraction is attributable to climate change (which is referred to as “carbon-climate feedback”). The carbon cycle diagnostic experiments (expts. 5.4 and 5.5 in the table below) provide a way of diagnosing the components of the total carbon cycle responses and the roles they play in carbon cycle feedback. This analysis can be used to analyze carbon cycle responses in conjunction with either of two experiments (or both): 1) the 1%/year CO₂ simulation (expt. 6.1), or 2) the historical and RCP4.5 simulations (expts. 3.2 and 4.1). The importance of carbon-climate feedback can be quantified from these simulations in terms of allowable emissions or airborne fraction.

The set of experiments listed in Table 5 is based on C⁴MIP design.¹² *If a coupled carbon/climate model is unable to achieve an approximately balanced pre-industrial carbon budget, it may not be sensible to perform these prescribed anthropogenic emissions runs, but for other coupled carbon/climate models these experiments are included in the core set.*

¹² Friedlingstein, P., P. Cox, R. Betts, L. Bopp, W. vonBloh, V. Brovkin, P. Cadule, S. Doney, M.Eby, . Kato, M. Kawamiya, W. Knorr, K. Lindsay, H.D. Mathews, T. Raddatz, P. Rayner, C. Reick, E. Roeckner, K.G. Schnitzler, R. Schnur, K. Strassmann, A.J. Weaver, C. Yoshikawa, and N. Zeng (2006): Climate-carbon cycle feedback analysis: Results from the C4MIP Model Intercomparison. *J. Climate*, **19**, 3337-3353, doi:10.1175/JCLI3800.1.

Table 5. Additional simulations with *fully coupled carbon/climate models only*. In expts. 5.1-5.3 the concentration of CO₂ is determined by the model, while in expts. 5.4 and 5.5 the evolving atmospheric CO₂ concentration is prescribed.

	#	Experiment	Notes	# of years
CORE	5.1	Pre-industrial control	Imposed conditions identical to expt. 3.1, but with CO ₂ concentration determined by the model itself.	250 (after spin-up period)
	5.2	Historical (1850- <u>at least</u> 2005)	As in expt. 3.2, but prescribe anthropogenic CO ₂ emissions, rather than concentrations.	≥ 156
	5.3	RCP8.5 (2006-2100)	Continuation of expt.5.2 into the future as in expt. 4.2, but with prescribed anthropogenic CO ₂ emissions, rather than concentrations.	95
TIER 1	5.4	experiment to diagnose strength of carbon/climate feedback	<p>This experiment is forced with prescribed atmospheric CO₂ concentrations. There are two acceptable options, <u>but options 1 is considered preferable and higher priority</u>:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> spin off from the control (expt. 3.1) at the same point as expt. 6.1 and impose conditions identical to those prescribed in expt. 6.1, but the radiation code is fed the time-invariant CO₂ concentration from the control. There is little climate change and the carbon cycle responds only to the increase in CO₂ concentration. spin off from the control (expt. 3.1) at the same point as expt. 3.2 and impose conditions identical to those prescribed in expt. 3.2 (for the historical period) and expt. 4.1 (RCP4.5 for the future), but the radiation code is fed the time-invariant CO₂ concentration from the control. The radiation code "sees" all other prescribed conditions evolve as in expts. 3.2 and 4.1. There will be some climate change in this case due the variations in, for example, aerosol forcing, solar variability, and land use change. 	140 (for option 1); 251 (for option 2)
TIER 2	5.5	Experiment to further understanding of carbon/climate feedback	<p>This simulation is forced with prescribed atmospheric CO₂ concentration. There are two options (<u>with option 1 preferred</u>), as in expt. 5.4, but this time only the radiation code "sees" the rising atmospheric CO₂ concentration (and under option 2 all the other evolving forcings found in expts. 3.2 and 4.1 should also be seen by the radiation code). Forced in this way, the carbon cycle, which "sees" the 3.1 control atmospheric CO₂ concentration, responds to climate change alone.</p>	140 (for option 1); 251 (for option 2)

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Purposes and key diagnostics:

The purposes of the prescribed anthropogenic emissions simulations include those enumerated for the prescribed concentration runs (Tables 3 and 4).

5.1 Pre-industrial control

a) See expt. 3.1

5.2 and 5.3 Historical and highest future emissions scenario

a) For the historical period and for an RCP 8.5 emissions scenario, provide estimates of future anthropogenic climate change with carbon climate feedbacks impacting atmospheric CO₂ and climate.

5.4 Experiment to diagnose strength of carbon/climate feedback

a) Diagnose the carbon climate feedback strength by comparing atmospheric CO₂ concentration to expt. 6.1 (option 1) or expts. 3.1 and 4.1 (option 2).

5.5 Run to diagnose components of carbon-climate feedback

a) Permits separation of the effect of climate change from atmospheric CO₂ increase.

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Further notes and issues that need to be considered include the following:

- 1) For the historical simulation (expt. 5.2), it is recommended that the recently produced gridded fossil fuel emissions data from Andres (hosted by IPSL) and the the land use data from Houghton (hosted at MPI) be used. More information can be found at the CMIP5 website.
- 2) Expts. 5.4 and 5.5 are designed to isolate the climate change effects on carbon uptake from the uptake due to CO₂ concentration increases (in the absence of climate change). The above table shows two options proposed for these experiments: analyze 1%/yr CO₂ increase runs or analyze historical+RCP4.5 runs. At the WGCM meeting in October 2011 and in subsequent discussion, it was decided that for groups who have not yet performed these experiments, it would be better to base these runs on the idealized 1%/yr CO₂ increase (rather than the historical+RCP4.5 simulations). There will, of course, also be interest in the historical+RCP4.5 runs, so groups who have already done these runs, should contribute them to the archive.

d. Diagnostic experiments for understanding the long-term simulations.

A key question is: “why, exactly, do models respond differently when forced similarly?” Interpretation of model differences in response to imposed forcing is easiest in the context of idealized experiments in which increases in atmospheric CO₂ concentration are prescribed and all other forcing (e.g., aerosols) is omitted. In particular these experiments are performed to evaluate the strength of various feedbacks that contribute to differences in response. In addition to the traditional benchmark CMIP experiment in which CO₂ concentration increases by 1% per year to obtain the transient climate response (TCR, the globally averaged surface air temperature change at the time of CO₂ doubling), related complementary experiments will be performed to isolate different

components of the response (including “fast” responses, often referred to as “forcing”, and “slower” responses, often referred to as “feedbacks”, as well as different aspects of carbon cycle responses). Table 6 lists the experiments required for a response analysis of this kind. These prescribed concentration experiments should be done with both coupled carbon/climate models and models without a carbon cycle.

The understanding of why models differ in this set of idealized experiments should provide a partial explanation for their differences in the more realistically “forced” runs (i.e., the historical runs and “future scenarios” in Tables 3-5).

In the Hansen-style¹³ experiments (6.2a,b, 6.4a,b, 6.5, 6.7b), the impact of CO₂ on the system is gauged while preventing response of the major slowly responding component (i.e., the ocean). This isolates the “fast” responses such as the direct impact of CO₂ on radiation, stratospheric adjustment, and fast cloud and land surface responses.

The Gregory-style¹⁴ analysis (applied to expt. 6.3) is a regression approach, which provides a good estimate of the equilibrium climate sensitivity and the strength of some of the feedbacks that are tied to global mean temperature change.

¹³ Hansen, J., Mki. Sato, R. Ruedy, L. Nazarenko, A. Lacis, G.A. Schmidt, G. Russell, I. Aleinov, M. Bauer, S. Bauer, N. Bell, B. Cairns, V. Canuto, M. Chandler, Y. Cheng, A. Del Genio, G. Faluvegi, E. Fleming, A. Friend, T. Hall, C. Jackman, M. Kelley, N. Kiang, D. Koch, J. Lean, J. Lerner, K. Lo, S. Menon, R. Miller, P. Minnis, T. Novakov, V. Oinas, Ja. Perlwitz, Ju. Perlwitz, D. Rind, A. Romanou, D. Shindell, P. Stone, S. Sun, N. Tausnev, D. Thresher, B. Wielicki, T. Wong, M. Yao, and S. Zhang (2005): Efficacy of climate forcings. *J. Geophys. Res.* **110**, D18104, doi:10.1029/2005JD005776.

¹⁴ Gregory, J. M., W. J. Ingram, M. A. Palmer, G. S. Jones, P. A. Stott, R. B. Thorpe, J. A. Lowe, T. C. Johns, and K. D. Williams (2004): A new method for diagnosing radiative forcing and climate sensitivity, *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, **31**, L03205, doi:10.1029/2003GL018747. (See also Gregory, J.M., and M. J. Webb, (2008): Tropospheric adjustment induces a cloud component in CO₂ forcing. *J. of Climate*, **21**, 58-71, doi:10.1175/2007JCLI1834.1.)

Table 6. Diagnostic experiments for understanding the long-term simulations.

	#	Experiment	Notes	# of years
CORE	6.1	Idealized 1%/yr run to 4x <u>pre-industrial</u> CO ₂ .	This run is initialized from the pre-industrial control (expt. 3.1) and CO ₂ concentration is prescribed to increase at 1%/yr.	140
	6.2a	Baseline for prescribed SST experiments (6.2b, 6.4a,b).	An atmosphere-only run driven by prescribed SST and sea ice consistent with the climatology of the pre-industrial control run (expt. 3.1)	≥30
	6.2b	Perturbed run for Hansen-style diagnosis of “fast” climate system responses to 4xCO ₂ .	As in expt. 6.2a above, but with atmospheric CO ₂ concentration quadrupled <u>relative to pre-industrial level</u> .	≥30
	6.3	Gregory-style diagnosis of “slow” climate system responses.	Impose an instantaneous quadrupling of atmospheric CO ₂ concentration (relative to pre-industrial) and then hold it fixed.	150
TIER 1	6.3-E	Ensemble of runs to improve the estimate of the “fast” climate response diagnosed with the Gregory method.	Generate an ensemble of runs <u>initialized in different months of the year and terminated after year 5, but otherwise</u> as in expt. 6.3. <u>[Counting the initial segment of expt. 6.3, the ensemble size will be 12.]</u>	11x5
	6.4a & 6.4b	Hansen-style diagnosis of “fast” climate system responses to all anthropogenic aerosols (6.4a) and to sulfate aerosols (6.4b) alone for the year 2000.	As in expt. 6.2a above, but with aerosols consistent with conditions in year 2000 of the historical run (expt. 3.2)	≥2x30
	6.5	Cloud response to imposed 4xCO ₂ (Hansen-style diagnosis of “fast” climate system responses).	Consistent with CFMIP requirements, the AMIP conditions are imposed (expt. 3.3, which is the control for this run), but the radiation code (only) sees quadrupled CO ₂ <u>relative to AMIP</u> .	30
	6.6	Cloud response to an imposed change in SST pattern.	Consistent with CFMIP requirements, add a patterned SST perturbation to the AMIP SSTs of expt. 3.3 (which is the “control” for this run).	30
	6.7a	Aqua-planet : control run	Consistent with CFMIP requirements (<u>with CO₂ set to AMIP mean concentration</u>), impose zonally uniform SSTs on a planet without continents.	5
	6.7b	Aqua-planet: cloud response to imposed 4xCO ₂ (Hansen-style diagnosis).	Consistent with CFMIP requirements, impose 4xCO ₂ (<u>relative to AMIP mean CO₂</u>) on the zonally uniform SSTs of expt. 6.7a (which is the control for this run).	5
	6.7c	Aqua-planet: cloud response to an imposed uniform change in SST.	Consistent with CFMIP requirements, add a uniform +4K to the zonally uniform SSTs of expt. 6.7a (which is the control for this run).	5
TIER 2	6.8	Cloud response to an imposed uniform change in SST	Consistent with CFMIP requirements, add a uniform +4 K SST to the AMIP SSTs of expt. 3.3 (which is the “control” for this run).	30

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Purposes and key diagnostics:

6.1 Idealized 1%/yr run

- a) Measure transient climate sensitivity.
- b) Evaluate model response under idealized forcing (without the complications of aerosols, land-use changes, etc.)
- c) Compare to previous CMIP model results (e.g., CMIP3 results).
- d) For models with full representation of the carbon cycle, the surface fluxes of CO₂ will be saved in order to calculate allowable emissions implied by the prescribed changes in atmospheric CO₂ and the uptake/release of CO₂ by the oceans and terrestrial biosphere. The separate effects on these surface fluxes of climate change alone (i.e., the carbon cycle feedback) and CO₂ concentration changes alone can be estimated by comparing the allowable emissions in expt. 6.1 with those found in expt. 5.4 and 5.5 (if option 1 is selected, as described in Table 5).

6.2a Baseline for prescribed climatological prescribed SST experiments that will estimate the CO₂ and aerosol radiative forcings (expts. 6.2b and 6.4a,b)

6.2b Hansen-style diagnostic.

- a) Determine the “fast” radiative responses to imposed changes in CO₂. The impact on TOA radiation provides an estimate of CO₂ “radiative forcing” + stratospheric adjustment and “fast” responses of the troposphere/land surface region.
- b) Determine the “fast” carbon cycle responses to imposed changes in CO₂. The different surface carbon flux responses among models may provide, for example, information concerning differences in CO₂ “fertilization” of vegetation.

6.3 Abrupt quadrupling of CO₂.

- a) Evaluate the equilibrium climate sensitivity of the model following the Gregory regression approach. This is the only expt. that will allow us to determine climate sensitivity.
- b) The experiment is initiated from the same point in the pre-industrial control run as expt. 6.1 (at least 150 years before the end of the control).
- c) Diagnose the strength of various feedbacks.
- d) Alternate estimate the “fast” radiative response (but this estimate will likely be noisier than in 6.2b.)

6.3-E Additional simulations with abrupt quadrupling of CO₂

- a) Obtain a refined estimate of the “fast” radiative responses using the Gregory method.
- b) Evaluate “fast” changes in carbon exchange between ocean and atmosphere. This component of carbon cycle response cannot be easily obtained from expts. 6.2a,b, thus this experiment may be particularly helpful in determining whether the “slow” or “fast” responses are primarily responsible for the differences found in coupled carbon/climate models.
- c) Each simulation is initiated from the same control run as expt. 6.3, but starting in a different month. So, for example if 6.3 were initialized in

January of year 300, the next ensemble member would be initialized in February of year 300.

- 6.4a,b Two Hansen-style diagnostic simulations to determine: 6.4a) total anthropogenic aerosol forcing for the year 2000, and 6.4b) sulfate aerosol forcing for the year 2000.
- 6.5 CFMIP experiment to diagnose the fast cloud adjustment to CO₂ radiative forcing, which is known to explain part of inter-model differences in cloud response. Note that in this experiment and in its control (i.e., the AMIP expt. 3.3), CFMIP recommends that the terrestrial carbon cycle model be inactivated and vegetation characteristics be prescribed (based on observations). If the carbon cycle remains active, it should continue to “see” 1xCO₂, while the radiation should see 4xCO₂ (nb. this is 4 times the CO₂ concentration prescribed in the AMIP expt. 3.3). This will isolate the cloud “fast” adjustments to CO₂ from those caused by changes in evapotranspiration (due, for example, to possible stomatal responses to CO₂ increase).
- 6.6 CFMIP experiment to examine cloud feedbacks and responses to a prescribed change in SSTs, and isolate the role of atmospheric processes in the response of clouds and precipitation to global warming. The pattern of SST change will be derived from a composite of the CMIP3 OAGCM response at time of CO₂ quadrupling. It will be provided by CFMIP.
- 6.7 CFMIP aqua-planet experiment to examine model differences and responses under simplified conditions. The ‘control’ experiment (expt. 6.7a) will use a zonally-uniform distribution of SST, no sea-ice at high latitudes, perpetual equinoctial conditions, and CO₂ concentration set to the mean of the AMIP period (the design of this experiment will be close to that proposed by Neale and Hoskins 2001). Expt. 6.7b would be similar to expt. 6.7a except that 4xCO₂ concentration (relative to the control) would be imposed to examine the fast adjustment of clouds and precipitation to CO₂ radiative forcing. Expt. 6.7c would be similar to expt. 6.7a except that a uniform +4K SST perturbation would be imposed to examine the response of clouds and precipitation to global warming.
- 6.8 CFMIP experiment to diagnose the cloud feedbacks and responses to a prescribed uniform +4 K change in SST.

Further notes and issues that need to be considered include the following:

- 1) These idealized runs will be initiated from the pre-industrial control run (expt. 3.1), and except as noted in Table 6 the same time invariant concentration/emissions/forcing should be imposed as in the control run.
- 2) In expts. 6.2a,b and 6.4a,b, the SST and sea ice values should come from a climatology of the pre-industrial control run (expt. 3.1). Daily values may be simply linearly interpolated between the monthly mean climatological values; it is not required that the climatological monthly means be recovered exactly from the daily time-series.
- 3) In all the prescribed SST experiments, land cover should be prescribed. That is, although vegetation might respond (e.g., the leaf area index), vegetation maps

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should be fixed consistent with the climatology of the pre-industrial control (as would, of course, land-use).

- 4) The Gregory-style experiments (6.3) are performed instead of the traditional CMIP atmosphere-mixed layer ocean (or slab) model experiments. This is because some groups no longer routinely develop this kind of model in the course of developing new versions of their AOGCMs and ESMs. However, if groups have the capability of running a slab coupled to the atmosphere to compute the equilibrium climate sensitivity, they are encouraged to do so, particularly if they can also perform experiments 6.3 to compare to the slab result.
- 5) As in all other experiments, models that include a carbon cycle should in prescribed SST experiments (i.e., 3.3, 6.2a,b, 6.4a,b, and 6.5) save the terrestrial carbon fluxes and also (if not too difficult) the ocean carbon fluxes.
- 6) Results for the prescribed SST simulations should be reported for all months run, including the initial transient period.
- 7) During at least one year of simulation 6.2a, the traditional method of estimating radiative forcing at the surface and top of the atmosphere should be applied in which two calls to the radiation code are made each time step, once with $1xCO_2$ and then with $4xCO_2$ (relative to pre-industrial level), but with only the heating rates from the $1xCO_2$ actually impacting the model. This will isolate the immediate impact of quadrupling CO_2 (before various other “fast” responses occur).
- 8) Expts. 6.5 to 6.8 (along with the AMIP run, expt. 3.3) are CFMIP experiments which aim to isolate the role of atmospheric processes in the response of clouds and precipitation to prescribed CO_2 radiative forcing and SST perturbations. Expts. 6.5, 6.6 (Tier 1) and 6.8 (Tier 2) are performed in ‘realistic’ conditions while expts. 6.7a,b,c (Tier 1) are performed in ‘simplified’ (aqua-planet) conditions. The ‘control’ run of the experiments run in ‘realistic’ conditions is the AMIP run (expt. 3.3). These short, atmosphere-only experiments may be run by all types of models (ESMs, OAGCMs, very high-resolution models, chemistry-climate models and NWP models).

e. Simulations for climate change detection and attribution studies.

In order to attribute observed climate change to particular causes, it is essential to perform simulations of the historical period (so-called 20th century runs) with only a subset of known forcing. Multi-member ensembles are useful because the forced response can be better determined. Experiments for this purpose are listed in Table 7.

The purpose of these experiments is to determine whether model predicted responses to various forcing is identifiable in the observational record. The larger the ensemble, the better determined will be the forced response (i.e., the signal). Note also that at the WGCN meeting in 2010 it was agreed that these simulations should be extended to the present and near future (year 2012), as discussed under note 12) of Table 3 above.

Table 7. Simulations for climate change detection and attribution studies.

	#	Experiment	Notes	# of years
TIER 1	7.1	Natural-only (1850- <u>at least</u> 2005)	Impose conditions as in the control experiment (3.1), but with natural forcing (e.g., volcanoes and solar variability) evolving as in the historical run (expt. 3.2).	≥ 156
	7.2	GHG-only (1850- <u>at least</u> 2005)	Impose conditions as in the control experiment (3.1), but with greenhouse gas forcing evolving as in the historical run (expt. 3.2). This can yield an estimate of the contribution of greenhouse gas forcing to recent warming, and when used in combination with the “all forcings” experiment (3.2) and “natural-only forcings experiment (3.1), the response to aerosols can be estimated as a residual.	≥ 156
	7.3	Other individual forcing runs	Consider, for example, land use changes only, or anthropogenic aerosols only or anthropogenic sulfate aerosols only, or volcanic aerosols only, etc.	$(\geq 1) \times (\geq 156)$
TIER 2	7.1-E, 7.2-E, 7.3-E	Individual forcing ensembles	Create multi-member ensembles for expts. 7.1-7.3, initialized from different points in the control run (expt. 3.1). Natural-only is highest priority with GHG-only next.	$(\geq 1) \times (\geq 2) \times (\geq 156)$